

Phytochemical Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants : Nonacosan-6-one from *Cassia auriculata* Linn.

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The pod husk of *Cassia auriculata* was exhaustively extracted with benzene. The benzene extract on further processing by chromatographic method yielded two white compounds which have been identified by spectral studies and chemical degradation as Nonacosane and Nonacosan-6-one. The ketone was not reported earlier.

CASSIA auriculata Linn. (Leguminosae) is a small perennial shrub growing widely in dry regions of central India, western peninsula and western Rajasthan. The bark is astringent and is valuable tanning material. Fruits are anthelmintic, flowers and pods are used in diabetes and urinary disorders¹. Literature survey revealed that not much chemical work has so far been done on this plant. The isolation of β -sitosterol, saponins and sapogenins from seeds², flavonoids from bark³, leaves⁴ and flowers⁵ and anthraquinones from leaves have been reported⁶. But pods of this plant have not been investigated for their chemical constituents. It was, therefore, proposed to study it in detail. The present paper deals with the structure elucidation of a new ketone Nonacosan-6-one which was not reported earlier in literature.

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined on a hot plate apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on Beckmann Model and nmr on Varian A-60 D spectrometer in $\text{CCl}_4/\text{CDCl}_3$ with TMS as internal standard.

Isolation of Nonacosane and Nonacosan-6-one: Dried and powdered pod husk of *C. auriculata* (5 kg) collected from Pali and Jodhpur districts (Rajasthan, India) was extracted with benzene in a soxhlet apparatus for 30 hrs. The extract was concentrated to 250 ml and absorbed on silica gel (50 g). This was fed on the top of silica gel column (2 cm \times 100 cm) and was eluted with petroleum ether and petroleum ether-benzene mixture. It yielded two colourless crystalline compounds CA-1, and CA-2.

Compound CA-1, colourless crystalline m.p. 63°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 2920, 2850, 1470, 1380, 1305, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} . NMR (δ , CDCl_3): 0.95, 1.20, m/e; 408 (M^+) 84, 71, 57, 43 and 23 (Found: C, 85.32; H, 14.73%; M^+ 408; $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{60}$ requires C, 85.29; H, 14.17%; mol. wt. 408).

Compound CA-2, colourless prisms m.p. 81°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 2910-20, 2850, 1700-10, 1225, 1125 and 720 cm^{-1} . NMR (δ , CDCl_3) 0.90, 1.3 and 2.4 (Found C, 85.25; H,

11.20%; M^+ 422; $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{58}\text{O}$ requires C, 85.10; H, 11.11% mol. wt. 422)

2:4 Dinitrophenyl hydrazone of CA-2: CA-2 (20 mg) in a 50 ml round bottom flask together with a clear solution of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone (30 mg) in methanol (4 ml) and 6N HCl (0.1 ml) was refluxed (5 min) on a water bath. Water (1 ml) was added dropwise to the hot solution till cloudiness appeared. It was cooled and filtered. The pale yellow crystals were recrystallised from aqueous methanol (80%) to give red orange needles (22 mg) m.p. 128°. The purity of hydrazone was checked by tlc. (Found: C, 69.82; H, 10.25; N, 9.27% $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{55}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 69.74; H, 10.30; N, 9.33%).

Oxidation of CA-2: The compound CA-2 (200 mg) was dissolved in 1, 2-dichloroethane (70 ml) and cooled in ice. To this cold solution a mixture consisting of trifluoroacetic anhydride (2 ml), 1,2-dichloroethane (2 ml) and H_2O_2 (90%, 10 ml) was gradually added. The contents were warmed on a water bath and the reaction continued at 50° for 45 min. The mixture was then cooled when a test sample responded to ferric hydroxamate test for ester. The unused trifluoroacetic acid (b.p. 72°) and the solvent 1, 2-dichloroethane (b.p. 84°) were removed by distillation. The remaining crude was recrystallised from hot methanol to remove minor impurities and a pure compound II (160 mg) m.p. 58° was obtained. IR (KBr): 1740(5) cm^{-1} instead of 1700-10(5) cm^{-1} .

Reductive fission of the Ester (II): Sodium (120 mg) and dry toluene (5 ml dried over sodium) were placed in a three necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer and a separating funnel and the flask heated on a heating mantle until the sodium melted. The molten sodium was converted to finely divided form by stirring. Heating was stopped but stirring continued to keep the sodium finely divided. It was cooled to about 80° and a solution of the ester (II, 140 mg) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was added from the separating funnel and followed by ethanol (40 ml) added rapidly (within 3 minutes). After the reaction subsided the

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flask was heated on a steam bath until the sodium completely dissolved. The mixture was then steam distilled.

Results and Discussion

Petroleum ether extract of pod husk on column chromatography yielded two white compounds, CA-1 and CA-2. CA-1 m.p. 63°, $C_{29}H_{56}$ was identified as Nonacosane on the basis of its ir (ν_{max} 2910, 2850, 1470 and 1380 cm^{-1}), nmr (in $CDCl_3$ 0.95 and 1.25) Mass (M^+ 408, M/e 29, 43, 57, 71,.....) cochromatography, m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectrum.

The compound CA-2 was characterised as Nonacosan-6-one on the basis of chemical reactions and spectral studies.

Elemental analysis and molecular ion peak at M^+ 422 in its mass spectrum confirmed the molecular formula for CA-2 to be $C_{29}H_{58}O$. Its ir spectrum showed a strong peak at 1710 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of C=O group. It formed mono-2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative. The position of keto group was further confirmed by its oxidation according to the method of Baeyer and Villiger⁷, modified by Hawthorne⁸ as well as by the fragmentation pattern of its mass spectrum.

The compound CA-2 on oxidation with trifluoro acetic anhydride and hydrogen peroxide gave a waxy product which gave a positive ferric hydroxamate test for ester. It was recrystallised from hot methanol as white waxy compound (II) $C_{29}H_{58}O_2$ m.p. 58°. The absence of a peak at 1710 cm^{-1} and appearance of a new peak at 1740 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of II indicated the cleavage of ketonic group to an ester group. The reductive fission of II by sodium and ethanol gave a mixture of two primary alcohols as indicated by tlc. The two alcohols were separated and identified as *n*-hexanol and *n*-tricosanol. These reactions indicated the structure of CA-2 to be a long chain unsymmetric ketone having the carbonyl group at the sixth position.

The structure of CA-2 was further confirmed by spectral studies. The ir spectrum indicated strong

bands at 2910-20 and 2850 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric and symmetric CH-stretching vibrations, strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} due to C=O group, medium bands at 1225 and 1125 cm^{-1} for $CH_2-CO-CH_2$ and weak band at 720 cm^{-1} for alkyl long chain $-(CH_2)_2$ -rocking vibrations.

The nmr peaks at δ 0.95 due to CH_3 protons, at δ 1.3 due to $-CH_2-$ protons and δ 2.31 due to $CH_2-CO-CH_2$ protons also supported the proposed structure.

The mass fragmentation patterns of CA-2 was in complete agreement with the proposed structure as Nonacosan-6-one⁹. The intense peaks at m/e 351, 99 and 28 were due to the α -cleavage. The peaks at m/e 323 and 71 were due to alkyl groups attached to carbonyl group. The peaks at m/e 366, 306, 114 and 56 were due to β -cleavage which occurred due to McLafferty rearrangement. The base peak at m/e 58 was accounted for $C_9H_6O^+$ fragment which might have resulted due to double McLafferty rearrangement as explained in Scheme 1.

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